

EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF THE NATIONAL RURAL HEALTH MISSION: A SURVEY-BASED ANALYSIS OF PUBLIC PERCEPTION AND HEALTH SECTOR IMPROVEMENTS IN INDIA

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Abstract:

The National Rural Health Mission (NRHM), implemented in India from 2005 to 2012, represented one of the largest government interventions in the public health sector, with an investment of nearly \$90 billion. This study aims to assess the NRHM's impact on the Indian public health system, particularly from the perspective of the general population. A random survey conducted across various Indian states, including both rural and urban areas, gathered data from 1,687 respondents, with 722 responses analyzed. The survey revealed that a significant majority of the population observed improvements in health services, particularly in rural and hard-to-reach areas. However, concerns such as corruption, inadequate infrastructure, and disparities in service delivery were also highlighted. Despite these challenges, the NRHM successfully enhanced public confidence in the health sector, with a notable preference for public health services over private alternatives. This study underscores the need for continued efforts to address the systemic issues identified and to build on the progress achieved under the NRHM.

Key words: *National Rural Health Mission; Indian Public Health; Person perception.*

Introduction:

The National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) was implemented in India from 2005 to 2012, during which the Government of India invested nearly \$90 billion in the public health sector. This substantial investment aimed to address the country's sluggish health indicators, which had been a concern since India's independence in 1947. Over the years, the NRHM's effectiveness has been the subject of extensive debate, with various claims and counterclaims regarding its successes and shortcomings, supported by an array of data.

To gauge the impact of NRHM as perceived by the general public, a survey was conducted from April to September 2011. The survey aimed to assess the changes in the public health sector as experienced by ordinary citizens. The findings indicated that, despite conflicting reports, NRHM successfully restored public confidence in the health sector, making it more accessible and responsive.

The NRHM was one of the most significant health interventions by the Indian government since independence. Successive Common Review Missions (CRMs) reported improvements in several health indicators during the program's implementation from April 2005 to March 2012. Various sources, including the Executive Summary on NRHM, Census data, Rural Health Surveys, District Level Household Surveys, and National Family Health Surveys, provide a wealth of data for evaluating the mission's achievements. However, the sheer volume and complexity of this data can be overwhelming for the general public, who primarily judge the program based on the services they receive from public health centers.

This survey was designed to evaluate public perceptions of NRHM and how the people of India viewed its outcomes. Random survey research, a key method in applied social research, was used for this purpose. Unlike sample surveys, which are typically more comprehensive and reliable but expensive, a random survey can still yield valuable insights, especially in a populous country like

India. The survey was conducted using a carefully designed paper-based questionnaire, and the results were analyzed using 'Survey System 10' software, with findings presented in charts and tables.

Methods:

2.1 Survey Sampling:

To collect data from a large population, a random sampling method was employed to minimize the survey's impact on resources. Instead of surveying the entire population, a random sample was deemed sufficient for drawing conclusions. This approach allowed for the discarding of certain results that were not representative. The survey targeted individuals aged 18 and above across various states in India, including Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, and West Bengal.

The random survey involved 1,687 participants, representing a diverse mix in terms of state, caste, community, gender, age, and geography. Out of the 1,050 respondents, 722 provided usable responses. The questionnaire was designed to elicit logical findings, with the responses analyzed across different variables.

2.2 Sample Size Calculation:

The sample size was determined using a sample size calculator provided by Creative Research Systems survey software. The random survey covered multiple states and included 1,687 individuals, with 1,050 responding to the questionnaire. Of these, 722 responses were analyzed. The participants were categorized by their socio-economic status, geographic location, and frequency of visits to public health centers, among other variables.

Results:

- **Socio-Economic Categories:** The survey divided respondents into Above Poverty Line (APL) and Below Poverty Line (BPL) categories. About 21% of the surveyed population belonged to the APL category, while the remaining 79% were in the BPL category, which is significant given that many NRHM schemes targeted the BPL population. You may please see in Table 1 and Chart 1.
- **Place of Residence:** The survey found that 47% of respondents lived in rural areas, 32% in hilly, tribal, or hard-to-reach areas, and 21% in urban areas such as metro cities or district headquarters. The high percentage of respondents from rural and remote areas underscores the NRHM's reach. You may please see in Table 2 and Chart 2.
- **Public Health Center Visits:** Approximately 80% of respondents visited a public health center at least once in the past seven years, with 11% visiting 1-5 times, 53% visiting 10-15 times, and 26% visiting more than 15 times. Notably, 11% of the surveyed population never visited a public health center during this period. You may please see in Table 3 and Chart 3.
- **Perception of Health Facilities:** Nearly 79% of respondents noticed improvements in health facilities over the last seven years, though 21% did not. Among those who noticed improvements, 37% were very satisfied, 58% were less satisfied, and 5% were disappointed with public health centers. You may please see in Tables 4 & and Charts 4 & 5.
- **Service Utilization:** The most accessed services were Outpatient Department (OPD) and immunization, with 33% and 61% of respondents using these services, respectively. Inpatient Department (IPD) and diagnostic services were utilized by about 6% of the population. You may please see in Table 6 and Chart 6.
- **Preference for Public vs. Private Health Sector:** Despite concerns, 74% of respondents preferred public health centers over private ones, a significant and surprising finding. You may please see in Table 7 and Chart 7.

- Perceived Issues: About 74% of respondents identified corruption as a prevalent issue in the public health system. Additionally, 16% cited poor infrastructure, 5% mentioned a lack of public amenities, and another 5% pointed to inadequate care at public health facilities. You may please see in Table 8 and Chart 8.
- Demographics: The survey sample consisted of 79% male respondents and 21% female respondents. You may please see in Table 9 and Chart 9.
- In table 10 a dropout analysis or quit ratio of the respondents are mentioned. Therefore, you may please see in table 10.

Conclusion:

The National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) significantly impacted India's public health landscape, particularly in rural and underserved regions. The survey results indicate that while the NRHM successfully revitalized public health services and restored public confidence, several challenges remain. Issues such as corruption, inadequate infrastructure, and service delivery disparities need to be addressed to sustain and build upon the progress made. The findings highlight the importance of ongoing reforms and targeted interventions to strengthen the public health sector further and ensure equitable access to quality healthcare for all citizens. The NRHM's success in re-establishing public trust in the health system provides a strong foundation for future health initiatives in India.

5. Declaration of Conflicting Interests

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7. Vitae:

This article authored by Krishnakant Sharma, a doctoral research scholar of Department of PMIR, Patna University. Formerly, he worked as Divisional Program Manager under the aegis of National Rural Health Mission with Jharkhand Government.

8. Tables:

Table 1: Select the category you belong...

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
APL	152 21%	152 100%	0 0%
BPL	570 79%	0 0%	570 100%

Table 2: You reside in.....

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
Rural area	342 47%	0 0%	342 60%
Urban area	38 5%	38 25%	0 0%
Metro City	38 5%	38 25%	0 0%
District Hq.	0	0	0

	0%	0%	0%
		0%	0%
State Hq.	76 11%	76 50%	0 0%
		100%	0%
Hilly area	228 32%	0 0%	228 40%
		0%	100%

Table 3: How many times you or family in general visited any public health centre during last seven years?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
1-5	76 11%	76 50%	0 0%
		100%	0%
5-10	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
		0%	0%
10-15	380 53%	0 0%	380 67%
		0%	100%
More than 15	190 26%	0 0%	190 33%

		0%	100%
Never	76 11%	76 50%	0 0%
		100%	0%

Table 4: Do you notice improvements in health facilities in last seven years?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
Yes	570 79%	0 0%	570 100%
No	152 21%	152 100%	0 0%

Table 5: How much you feel satisfied with improvements?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
Very satisfied	266 37%	0 0%	266 47%
Little satisfied	418 58%	114 75%	304 53%
Unsatisfied	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
Very disappointing	38 5%	38 25%	0 0%
		100%	0%

Table 6: Which service most reliable?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	684	114	570
OPD	228 33%	38 33%	190 33%
IPD	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
Immunization	418 61%	76 67%	342 60%
Ambulance	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
JSY	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
Free medicines	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
Diagnostics	38 6%	0 0%	38 7%
		0%	100%

Table 7: Do you prefer private sector more than public health sector?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL

	Base	722	152	570
Yes	190 26%	152 100%	38 7%	570 20%
No	532 74%	0 0%	532 93%	100%

Table 8: What are main weaknesses in public health sector according to you?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
Corruption	532 74%	76 50%	456 80%
Infrastructure	114 16%	0 0%	114 20%
Public amenities	38 5%	38 25%	0 0%
Doctors	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
Paramedics	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
Medicines	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
Adequate care	38 5%	38 25%	0 0%
		100%	0%

Table 9: Are you a male of female?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
Male	570 79%	152 100%	418 73%
Female	152 21%	0 0%	152 27%
		0%	100%

9. Charts:

Table 10: Dropout Analysis*Quit Percentage Base: All Questionnaires*

S. No	Question	Ans	% age	Change	Quit
1	Select the category you belong...	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%
2	You reside in.....	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%
3	How many times you or family in general visited any	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%
4	Do you notice improvements in health facilities in last seven years?	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%
5	How much you feel satisfied with improvements?	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%
6	Which service most reliable?	684	95%	-5.3%	0.0%
7	Do you prefer private sector more than public health sector?	722	100%	5.3%	0.0%
8	What are main weaknesses in public health sector according to you?	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%
9	Are you a male of female?	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%

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